

EFFECTIVENESS OF SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS IN MATHEMATICS 3 IN SAN VICENTE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine if the use of supplementary materials was effective in improving the academic performance of Grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics 3 at San Vicente Elementary School, Glan 2 Division of Sarangani Province for the school year 2021-2022. This study used the pre-experimental design. Specifically, the researcher utilized the single group pre-test-posttest design. The respondents were the 30 grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics of San Vicente Elementary School Glan 2 District, Division of Sarangani composed of 15 boys and 15 girls, respectively. The statistical tools used to analyze and interpret the data gathered were the frequency counts, mean, and t-test to treat the relationship of the two variables under study. Based on the findings, it was found out that the supplementary materials were effective and had improved the performance of Grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics.

Keywords: Supplementary materials, Mathematics 3, pre-experimental design, education, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics has continually been given special the attention in school, related to many other fields and disciplines. Some learners struggled with Mathematics because of dyscalculia. A learning difficulty causes learners to work with formulas, shapes, and number-related concepts. It made it difficult for them to understand and manage Math problems. These learners usually fell far behind their colleagues in Math and had trouble with a number-related problem that did not improve with ongoing practices. The learners struggled with Mathematics because they did not have the proper foundation to succeed. These learners had fallen behind in a unit or moved on to advanced material before they were ready, leading to failing grades (The National Council of Mathematics, 2020; Wilkey, Pollack, and Price, 2020; Lee, 2019; Ganor-Stern, 2017).

On the other hand, Mathematics effectively built mental discipline and encouraged logical reasoning and mental rigors among young people. It consisted of numeracy, the decimal system, arithmetic operations, and the capacity to solve elementary arithmetic problems such as proportionality, knowledge of magnitudes, and knowledge of common two-and three-dimensional geometric forms. Numeracy among early graders was a critical literacy skill. It played an essential role in early development. The child could only access the power of education first through a numerical he was familiar with where the learner developed his self-confidence, pride, and full potential. Mathematical literacy needed to function in life. This involved skills not taught in the classroom, like using numbers and solving problems in real life. The early mathematical achievement of children had constituted an infrastructure for their academic success in the future (Morsanyi, et al., 2018; Nirit, Hadad Bat-Sheva, and Orly, 2021; Freeman, 2018).

A self-learning module is an orderly set of instructions designed to facilitate learners' mastery of a body of knowledge or a procedure. When combined with other modules, learners can master a vast body of knowledge or a complex process. Moreover, self-learning modules are also defined as its name implies - modules, which are available for students to use by them for learning on their own and usually do not require any teacher for help. Given that the use of these modules entirely relies on the hands of students, and these are self-learning materials will aid students to learn and do at their own pace and interest (Maile and Cooper, 2014).

On July 1, 2020, the Philippines Department of Education released a new normal press statement. As the Department is committed to preparing for the opening of the School Year 2020-2021, DepEd will provide Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) and alternative learning delivery modalities for the majority types of learners across the entire Philippines. Meanwhile, the integration of SLMs with alternative learning delivery modalities such as modular, television-based, radio-based teaching, blended, and online will assist DepEd in ensuring that all students have access to high-quality primary education for this school year. At the same time, face-to-face classes were still strictly prohibited due to the public current health situation (Agaton and Cueto, 2021; Guimalon, 2021).

Correspondingly with the above statements, the effectiveness of the SLMs was significant. Moreover, this quantitative study tried to gain a better understanding of its effectiveness. Therefore, the researcher in this study wanted to find out whether the Self-Learning Modules were effective in teaching and could these significantly improve the performance of pupils in Mathematics.

1.1. Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine if the use of supplementary materials was effective in improving the academic performance of Grade 3 struggling learners in San Vicente Elementary School, Glan 2 Division of Sarangani Province for the school year 2021-2022.

Specifically, this study answered the following subproblems:

1. What are the pretest scores of Grade 3 struggling learners before using supplementary materials in Mathematics?
2. After using the supplementary materials, what are the post-test scores of the subjects?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the Grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics after the treatment?

1.2. Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on different learning theories. First, it was based on the Transfer Theory by Fox (1983) cited by Jones (2017). It stated that Transfer Theory occurred when a teacher applied new information, strategies, and skills to which students had acquired new knowledge. The teachers who adopted this learning theory believed that knowledge could be transferred to students. It emphasized that the help of supplementary materials in delivering instruction directly impacted the learners' academic learning, needs, interests, and future endeavors.

Secondly, the Theory of Assimilation by Ausubel (1963), cited by Seel (2016), which focused on what he described as meaningful learning. It is a process where new information is related to an existing relevant aspect of the individuals' knowledge structure. This component of his theory fits with short-term and long-term memory concepts in cognitive information processing. This theory integrated the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. It further identified two aspects of learning, namely; rote learning, and meaningful learning. Rote learning is learning for a young learner which implied recall and transferability. In this theory, the learners were given the freedom to learn and how they wanted to learn.

The study's objective was to provide and promote supplementary materials for a faster learning process of numerical skills of the young learners to address the gap and contextualize it to fit target struggling young learners John Dewey (1897), cited by Williamson (2018), a learner learns by considering popular theories.

1.3. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The figure consists of two significant variables, the pretest, and the post-test scores.

The first box presents the pretest scores. The pre-test was given to the 30 struggling learners at the onset of the course to determine their initial awareness of the measures stated in the learning objectives.

The second box illustrates the post-test scores of the subjects. The administration of post-test was done after the treatment of two (2) months to determine whether the 30 Grade 3 struggling learners had improved their performance in Mathematics 3.

The results of pretest and post-test using supplementary materials were considered to assess the current numeracy skills of the 30 struggling Grade 3 learners and to find out if the supplementary materials were effective.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

2. METHOD

2.1 Research Design

This study used the pre-experimental design. Specifically, the researcher utilized the single-group pre-test-posttest design. According to Ardales (2008), as cited by Glenn (2016) the one-group pretest-post-test design is without a control group. However, it has a pretest or a baseline observation (O1), which allows the investigator to determine the effects of the treatment by comparing the pretest and post-test (O2) results. This design is subject to validity threats history, maturity, testing, instrumentation, and statistical regression. Its external validity is poor, as illustrated below.

The crafted supplementary material was the basis for determining the performance level of Grade 3 struggling learners. They underwent the Pretest and Post-test.

The supplementary materials were designed, and media choices were made in the design phase. In the development phase, supplemental materials were produced according to decisions made during the design phase. The implementation phase included testing additional tools with the target subjects, putting the product in total production, and orienting learners and teachers on how to use these tools. The evaluation stage included both the formative and summative, which provided opportunities for feedback from the users (Strickland, 2006 cited by Johnsen, 2020).

The purpose was not to formulate and test the theory but to develop effective products for use in school. Products were designed to meet specific needs and according to detailed specifications. Once completed, outcomes were field-tested and revised until a specified level of effectiveness was achieved (Rice, and Ortiz, 2021; Das, 2017).

2.2 Research Locale

The study was conducted in San Vicente Elementary School Glan 2 District Municipality of Glan, the Department of Education, Division of Sarangani, particularly in Glan. It comprised 24 teachers, and 586 pupils enrolled from kinder to Grade 6. The school is located at Barangay San Vicente Glan Sarangani Province residents in different communities vary that in their dialects like Cebuano, Muslim, Ilongo, Ilocanos, and Blaán.

In religion, almost 80 percent of the people in the community are Christians. Only 20 percent is composed of Muslims. Their source of income is based on agriculture, with high-level production of dried coconut meat, coconuts, corn, and banana. It is an agricultural barangay.

2.3 Research Respondents

The subjects underwent experimental procedures were the 30 Grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics of San Vicente Elementary School Glan 2 District Division of Sarangani. It was composed of 15 boys and 15 girls. Table 1 presents the distribution of the subjects.

Table 1: Distribution of the Subjects.

BOYS	GIRLS	TOTAL
15	15	30

The instruments used in this study were the Pre-test and Post-test constructed by the researcher coming from the supplementary materials. It was composed of 30 questions.

Initially, the proponent made a 60-item test instrument based on the second grading lesson. After formulating and completing the draft of the device, the researcher piloted it homogeneously to answer the chosen 30 grade 3 struggling learners in mathematics coming from a neighboring school. After the learners answered the instrument, it was immediately retrieved through Internal-Consistency Method. Using this method, one could determine if the examinee passed or failed in an item A (1) was assigned for a pass or a failure.

The process of obtaining a reliability coefficient in this method was determined using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20.

Where N is the number of items, SD^2 is the variance of scores on test defined as, and $\sum p_i q_i$ is the product of the proportion of passed and failed for item i. The symbol p_i denotes the proportion of individuals giving item 1, and the proportion failing by q_i , where $q_i = 1 - p_i$. The proponent strictly observed the steps in applying the Kuder-Richard Formula 20:

First, the researcher computed the variance SD^2 of the test scores for the whole group. Second, the researcher determined the proportion passing each item (p_i) and failing each item (q_i). Third, the researcher multiplied the (p_i) and (q_i) from each item and sum for all the things. It gave the $\sum p_i q_i$ value. Finally, the researcher substituted the calculated values in the formula.

After that, the researcher computed the values based on the computation that revealed if the 60-item test instrument piloted was reliable or not. Upon knowing the reliability of the tools, the proponent did an item analysis to see the index of difficulty and the index of discrimination of each item. To do this, the researcher strictly followed simple but effective procedures for item analysis:

Step 1, the researcher arranged the test scores from the highest to the lowest. Step 2, she got one-third of the papers from the highest and one-third from the lowest scores. The idle one-third was set aside. Step 3, she counted the number of students in the upper and lower groups, respectively, who chose the options. Step 4, she then recorded the frequency from step 3. Step 5, the proponent estimated the index of difficulty.

Where $\sum x$ is the sum of the correct answer of the upper and lower groups, and N is the number of cases in both the upper and lower groups. Difficulty refers to the percentage of getting the correct answer to each item. The smaller the percentage, the more complex the item is. The majority criterion (50% plus one) is the basis for interpreting the index of difficulty, whether the item is difficult or easy. When the item has a 50% difficulty index, it is neither easy nor difficult; the lower the percentage, the more complex the item is.

Finally, in step 6, the researcher estimated the item discriminating power. In evaluating the item discriminatory power, the upper and lower groups were compared to the correct responses.

To discuss the formula, RU presents the proper response of the upper group, RL is the appropriate response of the lower group, and NG is the member of learners in each group.

According to Calmorin (2014), the discriminating power of an item is not more than 1.00. A maximum of positive discriminator power is revealed by an index of 1.00. It is obtained when all upper group learners chose the correct answer and not the lower group. Negative discriminating power is obtained when more learners in the lower group get the correct answers than the upper group. Moreover, a zero-discriminating power (0.00) is attained when the equal frequency of the upper and lower groups received the right answer. The items having negative and zero discriminating power should be revised or improved. Table 2 presents the discrimination index and the difficulty of the test item.

Table 2: Index of Discrimination and Difficulty of test Item

INDEX OF DISCRIMINATION	ITEM EVALUATION
0.40 or higher	Very Good Item
0.30 – 0.39	Good Item

0.20 – 0.29	Marginal Item
0.19 or below	Poor Item
INDEX OF DIFFICULTY	ITEM EVALUATION
0.70 or higher	Low Difficulty
0.31 – 0.69	Moderate Difficulty
0.30 or below	High Difficulty

The proponent retained the items that passed the difficulty and discrimination index in the item analysis. Other items that marked revised or improved were carried out. The 60-item tests underwent face validation. It was validated by three (3) experts who are Master teachers. The instrument was validated using the following criteria: 1.) clarity of direction and indicators, 2.) presentation and organization, 3.) suitability of the items, 4.) adequacy of indicators per category, 5.) congruency to the purpose, 6.) impartiality of the researcher, and 7.) appropriateness of the options and evaluation rating system. Through their expertise, revisions and improvements were made. The instrument obtained an overall mean of **4.77**, which implied an excellent descriptive rating.

Out of the 60-item Test in Mathematics 3 that went through the validation and piloting process, the researcher came up with an official 30-item Test which was used in the pretest and post-test activities. The items were coming from the supplementary materials.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedures were religiously followed in the actual conduct of the study.

The researcher approached the principal, the district head, and the barangay, following the proper protocol for the COVID 19 pandemics: wearing of face mask, face shield, and hand sanitizer.

To ensure the transparency and validity of the instruments, the researcher submitted the tool for validation to five expert validators for critical analyses. Their comments and suggestions were considered to come up with the official questionnaire. Tests of validity, including Item analysis were done.

The subjects came from the grade 3 learners of San Vicente Elementary School. They were identified as the struggling learners. There were only 30 subjects being part of the study.

Having found the instrument valid and reliable, the researcher administered the questionnaire by observing the proper protocol; social distancing, wearing a face mask and face shield, and hand sanitizing. After the actual administration of the test, it was retrieved immediately.

Appropriate tools were used to analyze and interpret the gathered data. Problems number one and two were treated using frequency counts. The proponent employed the t-Test for correlated samples. It was used to answer problem number three.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pre-test Scores of Grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics

Table 3 below presents the data on the pretest scores of grade 3 struggling learners in mathematics before the treatment was given. It was utilized using the frequency counts and percentage distribution of the scores of the learners in the pretest.

It can be gleaned that out of the thirty (30) subjects, none of the learners got scores of 25 to 30. Learner numbers 4, 7, 9, and 16 obtained scores of 24, 19, 20, and 21, respectively. Learner numbers 1, 2, 3, 5, 11, 13, 19, 24, and 28 obtained scores of 18, 13, 15, 17, 16, 15, 13, 18, and 17, respectively. Learner numbers 8, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 26, 27, 29, and 30 got scores of 12, 10, 11, 7, 10, 9, 8, 9, 9, 10, 9, 8, 9, 8, and 9, respectively. Out of 30 respondents, only 2 learners namely learner numbers 6 and 10 had gained scores of 6 and 1, respectively.

These results were parallel to research on pupils who lacked supplementary materials in mathematics; they struggled to learn mathematics and with low prior knowledge in learning math. In that case, they most reflected on highlighted errors within an incorrect mathematical problem. Developing number sense from supplementary materials were beneficial for enhancing learners' importance in learning mathematics. Development in understanding mathematics were exciting and significant among learners when they realized its relevance to their daily lives (Reid 2015; Ramesh, 2012; Singh et al. 2018).

Table 3: Frequency counts and Percentage Distribution of Pretest Scores of grade 3 Pupils in Mathematics

Pupil	Frequency	Percentage	Description
1	18	60	Moderate
2	13	43	Moderate
3	15	50	Moderate
4	24	80	High
5	17	57	Moderate
6	6	20	Very Low
7	19	63	High
8	12	40	Low
9	20	67	High
10	1	3	Very Low
11	16	53	Moderate
12	10	33	Low
13	15	50	Moderate
14	11	37	Low
15	7	23	Low
16	21	70	High
17	10	33	Low
18	9	30	Low
19	13	43	Moderate
20	8	27	Low
21	9	30	Low
22	9	30	Low
23	10	33	Low
24	18	60	Moderate
25	9	30	Low
26	8	27	Low
27	9	30	Low
28	17	57	Moderate
29	8	27	Low
30	9	30	Low
TOTAL	371	1,236	
MEAN SCORE	12.4	41.2	Low

3.2 Post-Test Scores of Grade 3 struggling Learners in Mathematics

Table 4 presents the post-test scores of grade 3 struggling learners in mathematics after the treatment. The proponent used frequency counts and percentage distribution in analyzing the data.

It can be observed that an improvement was reflected. It was found out that out of 30 subjects, ten learners got very high scores. These were learner numbers 1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 11, 16, 24, and 28 obtained scores of 26, 25, 30, 30, 29, 25, 29, 30, 24, and 28, respectively.

On the other hand, 15 learners got higher scores and these were learner numbers 2, 8, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 26, and 27 obtained scores of 19, 21, 19, 21, 20, 21, 19, 22, 19, 20, 21, 20, 22, 19, and 20, respectively. As shown, there were four learners who got moderate scores. They were learner numbers 6, 15, 29, and 30 with obtained score of 15, 14, 17, and 18 respectively, while only one learner got under low score. Learner number 10 got a score of 11.

As a result, learners' knowledge increased after exposing them to different supplementary materials. Their numeracy skills were developed through a series of activities. It explored their thinking abilities. Hence, the teachers are encouraged to continuously use supplementary materials in mathematics to improve the teaching and learning process. Numeracy skills are increasingly formal among young learners to progress in number sense and conviction using mental and written strategies to solve problems. It stated that by the age of eight, learners should read and write numbers up to 999. They have

to start using tallies to keep track of totals. However, some kids still relied on essential pictures to explain problem-solving. The learners could utilize number lines to aid mental counting skills since they already comprehended numbers on a number line (Ahl, 2016; Cui, Xiao, Ma, Yuan, Kodash, and Zhou, 2020; Smith and Shillam 2015).

Table 4: Frequency counts and Percentage Distribution of Post-test Scores Of grade 3 Pupils in Mathematics

Pupil	Frequency	Percentage	Description
1	26	87	Very High
2	19	63	High
3	25	83	Very High
4	30	100	Very High
5	30	100	Very High
6	15	50	Moderate
7	29	97	Very High
8	21	70	High
9	25	83	Very High
10	11	37	Low
11	29	97	Very High
12	19	63	High
13	24	80	High
14	20	67	High
15	14	47	Moderate
16	30	100	Very High
17	21	70	High
18	19	63	High
19	22	73	High
20	19	63	High
21	20	67	High
22	21	70	High
23	20	67	High
24	27	90	Very High
25	22	73	High
26	19	63	High
27	20	67	High
28	28	93	Very High
29	17	57	Moderate
30	18	60	Moderate
TOTAL	660	2200	
MEAN SCORE	22	73	High

3.3 Effectiveness of the Supplementary Materials

Table 5 reflects the effectiveness of the supplementary materials in improving the academic performance of grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics. The t-test was used. The result revealed a significant difference at the .05 level with the df of 19. The required t-value of significance was 1.729. It was found that the computed t-value of 3.85 was higher than the tabular value of 1.699. This result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. It implied that the supplementary materials effectively improved the academic performance of Grade 3 struggling learners in Mathematics.

Additionally, the teacher applied new information, strategies, and skills to acquire new knowledge. Learning occurred and improved academic performance when task was given independently. It helped motivate by creating and encouraging them to use information from the given text and beyond learners' expectations. The supplementary learning materials helped the learners understand the concept and recognize their abilities to investigate, to explore, and to solve mathematical problems that increased their school's performance (Ahl, 2016; Dodd, 2015; Jones, 2017; Langat, 2020).

Moreover, research studies revealed that effective instructional materials enhanced learners' understanding of teaching and learning processes. It was also discovered that the improvised instructional materials brought the exact meaning compared

to the produced instructional materials (Himah, Parker and Asahe, 2018; LeFevre et al., 2009; Batchelor and Gilmore, 2015; Moran, 2016).

Finally, engaging pupils in educational activities using tangible material was one of the solutions. Based on the interview made by the experts, they found out that many teachers in the United employed activities in Mathematics lessons that helped in improving the learners' engagement and arithmetic learning outcomes. Based on the survey's results, many instructors regularly employed instructional activities utilizing various resources (Kaminski and Sloutsky, 2020).

Table 5: Effectiveness of the Supplementary Materials in Improving the Academic Performance of Grade 3 Struggling Learners in Mathematics.

Variable	df	t		Description	Decision
		Computed	Tabular		
Pre-test Mean Score versus Post test Mean Score	n-1 29	10.89	1.699	With significant difference at .05 level	Reject H ₀₃

REFERENCES

- [1] Abadi M., Asih, E. & Jupri, A. (2018). The development of interactive mathematics learning material based on local wisdom. *Journal Phys.: Conf. Ser.*1013012131. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1013/1/012131/pdf>.
- [2] Abubakar, H. O., Jemilat, I. A., & Oluranti, S. A. (2021). Availability and use of audio-visual materials for teaching mathematics at the Senior Secondary School in Ibadan, Southwest Local Government, Oyo State. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-17.
- [3] Acharya, B. (2017). Factors affecting difficulties in learning mathematics by mathematics learners. *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 6(2), 8-15.
- [4] Afni, N., & Hartono. (2020). Contextual teaching and learning (CTL) as a strategy to improve students' mathematical literacy. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1581(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1581/1/012043>.
- [5] Afthina, H., Mardiyana, & Pramudya, I. (2017). Think, pair share using realistic mathematics education approach in geometry learning. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 895(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/895/1/012025>.
- [6] Ahl, B. (2016). Research findings' impact on the representation of proportional reasoning in Swedish mathematics textbooks. REDIMAT52180-204.
- [7] Ahmed, M., Qureshi, M. N., Mallick, J., & Nabil, B. K. (2019). Selection of sustainable supplementary concrete materials using the osm-ahp-topsis approach. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2019, 12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2019/2850480>.
- [8] Alonso-Díaz, S. (2017). *Number representation in perceptual decisions* <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/number-representation-perceptual-decisions/docview/1965500888/se-2>.
- [9] Anderson, G. (2018). Measuring aspects of mobility, polarization, and convergence in the absence of cardinality: indices based upon transitional typology. *Social Indicators Research*, 139(3), 887-907. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11205-017-1767-1>.
- [10] Andika, W. D., Akbar, M., Yufiarti, & Sumarni, S. (2019). Playing board games with mathematical self-concept to support early numeracy skill of 5-6 years old children. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1166(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1166/1/012019>.
- [11] Anushree, B., Bernstein, D., Drayton, B., & McKenney, S. (2021). Designing educative curriculum materials in interdisciplinary teams: Designer processes and contributions. *Instructional Science*, 49(2), 249-286. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11251-021-09538-5>.

- [12] Anyim, W. O. (2018). Multimedia instructional resources for effective library user education program in universities in north-central, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/multimedia-instructional-resources-effective/docview/2163340523/se-2>.
- [13] Artemenko, C. (2021). Developmental front-parietal shift of brain activation during mental arithmetic across the lifespan: A registered report protocol. *PLoS One*, 16(8)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256232>.
- [14] Aruna, R., & Benson, A. (2020). A numbers game: Quantification of work, auto-gamification, and worker productivity. *American Sociological Review*, 85(4), 573-609. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0003122420936665>.
- [15] Askew, M., Venkat, H., Mathews, C., Ramsingh, V., Takane, T., & Roberts, N. (2019). Multiplicative reasoning: An intervention's impact on foundation phase learners' understanding. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 9(1) <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v9i1.622>.
- [16] Awolaju, B. (2016). Instructional materials correlate with students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools in Osun State. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(9),705-709.
- [17] Ayaz, A., Tabassum, R., & Farooq, R. A. (2017). An investigation of curriculum relevancy with the cognitive development (number conservation ability) during early childhood education. *Journal of Early Childhood Care and Education*, 1 <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/investigation-curriculum-relevancy-with-cognitive/docview/2362278610/se-2>.
- [18] Ayu Sri Menda, B. S., Sinulingga, K., & Eva, M. G. (2021). Development of guided inquiry-based instructional materials to improve students' science process skills. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1811(1) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1811/1/012099>.
- [19] Aziz, İ. (2021). The impact of game-based, modeling, and collaborative learning methods on the achievements, motivations, and visual, mathematical literacy perceptions. *Sage Open*, 11(1) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/21582440211003567>.
- [20] Badaruddin, D., Tengah, K. and Prahmana, R. (2018). Enhancing manipulation of the algebraic equations through the Balance Method. *Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* 1088 (2018) 012007. DOI:10.1088/1742-6596/1088/1/012007.
- [21] Badaruddin, D., Tengah, K. and Prahmana, R. (2018). Enhancing manipulation of the algebraic equation through the Balance Method. *Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* 1088 (2018) 012007. DOI:10.1088/1742-6596/1088/1/012007.
- [22] Bal, A. P. (2020). Attitudes and beliefs of primary school teaching undergraduate students towards mathematics and their effects on mathematics achievement. *Çukurova University.Faculty of Education Journal*, 49(2), 826-841. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14812/cufej.694626>.
- [23] Balala Maha, M. A., Shaljan, A., & Cairns, D. (2021). Investigating early numeracy activities and skills with mathematics dispositions, engagement, and achievement among fourth graders in the United Arab Emirates. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, 9(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40536-021-00106-4>.
- [24] Banker, S. M., Ramphal, B., Pagliaccio, D., Thomas, L., & Rosen, E. (2020). Spatial network connectivity and spatial reasoning ability in children with nonverbal learning disability. *Scientific Reports (Nature Publisher Group)*, 10(1).
- [25] Barbiera, and Booth. (2016). Support for struggling students in algebra: contributions of an incorrect worked example. *Learning and individual differences*. Vol. 48, pages 36-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2016.04.001>.
- [26] Barrington, M. (2015). Mathematics milestone of 7-8 years old. Kidspot. Australia, 2015. <https://www.kidspot.com.au/school/preschool/preschool-numeracy/mathematics-milestones-78/news-story/69384ccbfcefb74a3bb438430efe0383>.
- [27] Barth-Cohen, L., Braden, S. K., Young, T. G., & Gailey, S. (2021). Reasoning with evidence while modeling: Successes at the middle school level. *Physical Review. Physics Education Research*, 17(2) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevPhysEducRes.17.020106>.

- [28] Bellini, D., Crescentini, A., Zanolla, G., Cubico, S., Favretto, G., Faccincani, L., Ardolino, P., & Giancesini, G. (2019). Mathematical competence scale (mcs) for primary school: the psychometric properties and the validation of an instrument to enhance the sustainability of talents development through the numeracy skills. Assessment. *Sustainability*, 11(9) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su11092569>.
- [29] Berkowitz, T., Schaeffer, M., Maloney, E., Peterson, L., Gregor, C., Levine, S. C., & Beilock, S (2015). Math at home adds up to achievement in school between fluid intelligence and reading/mathematics: Effects of tasks, age, and social-economic status: psychological *Bulletin*, 145(2), 189.
- [30] Bezuidenhout, H. S. (2020). The interface between early numeracy, language and learning environments: Pedagogical implications. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 10(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v10i1.923>.
- [31] Björn, P., M., Äikäs, A., Hakkarainen, A., Kyttälä, M., & Fuchs, L. S. (2019). Accelerating mathematics word problem-solving performance and efficacy with think-aloud strategies. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 9(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v9i1.716>.
- [32] Boz, M., Uludağ, G., & Erdoğan, S. (2020). The effect of the manipulative materials on the early mathematical skills. *Bartın Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9(3), 492-500. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14686/buefad.620085>.
- [33] Braak, D., Kleemans, T., Størksen, I., Verhoeven, L., & Segers, E. (2018) Domain-specific effects of attentional and behavioral control in early literacy and numeracy development. *Learning and Individual Differences*. Volume 28. Pages 61-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2018.10.001>
- [34] Bransford, J., Brown, A. & Cocking, R. (2000). *How People Learn: Brain, mind, experience, and school*. Washington D. C.: National Academy Press.
- [35] Brase, G. (2021). Which individual cognitive differences predict good Bayesian reasoning? Concurrent comparisons of underlying abilities. *Memory & Cognition*, 49(2), 235-248.
- [36] Breen and O'Shea (2010). Mathematics thinking task design Irish math. Soc. Bulletin 66, 39-49.
- [37] Bryant, D. P., Pfannenstiel, K. H., Bryant, B. R., Roberts, G., Fall Anna-Mari, Maryam, N., & Lee, J. (2021). Improving the mathematics performance of second-grade students with mathematics difficulties through an early numeracy intervention. *Behavior Modification*, 45(1), 99-121. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0145445519873651>.
- [38] Bryant, D. P., Pfannenstiel, K. H., Bryant, B. R., Roberts, G., Fall Anna-Mari, Maryam, N., & Lee, J. (2021). Improving the mathematics performance of second-grade students with mathematics difficulties through an early numeracy intervention. *Behavior Modification*, 45(1), 99-121. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0145445519873651>.
- [39] Budac, A., Gareau-Brennan, C., Mucz, D., McNally, M. B., & Rathi, D. (2020). Numeracy programming at major Canadian urban libraries: An exploratory study. *Partnership: The Canadian Journal of Library and Information Practice and Research*, 15(1), 1-22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21083/partnership.15i1.4668>.
- [40] Callaman, R., & Itaas, E. (2020). Students' mathematics achievement in Mindanao context: A meta-analysis. *JRAMathEdu (Journal of Research and Advances in Mathematics Education)*, 5(2), 148-159.
- [41] Calmorin, L. P. & Calmorin, M. A. (2014). *Research Methods and Thesis Writing*. Rex Bookstore.
- [42] Capuno, R., Necesario, R., Etcuban, J. O., Espina, R., Padillo, G., & Manguilimotan, R. (2019). Attitudes, study habits, and academic performance of junior high school students in mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(3), 547-561.
- [43] Carreiras et al. (2015). Numbers are not like words: Different pathways for literacy and numeracy. *Neuroimage* Volume 118, Pages 79-78.
- [44] Cato, B. R. (2020). *Mathematics cognitive and content abilities across the vincentian student population*. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/mathematics-cognitive-content-abilities-across/docview/2456856524/se-2>.

- [45] Catts, H. W., McIlraith, A., Bridges, M. S., & Nielsen, D. C. (2017). Viewing a phonological deficit within a multifactorial model of dyslexia. *Reading and Writing*, 30(3), 613-629. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11145-016-9692-2>.
- [46] Chandrakala, B. S., Kate, N. N., Vadivel, K., & Zeba, A. (2019). Effect of hormones on cognitive abilities and skills. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy, and Pharmacology*, 9(8), 788-792. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5455/njppp.2019.9.09303201804062019>.
- [47] Chen, C., Law, V., & Huang, K. (2019). The roles of engagement and competition on learner's performance and motivation in game-based science learning. *Educational Technology, Research, and Development*, 67(4), 1003-1024. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11423-019-09670-7>.
- [48] Colen, J. (2019). *Elementary School Teachers' Conceptions of the Common Core State Standards for Mathematical Practice* (Order No. 13917982). Available from Publicly Available Content Database. (2244370710). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/elementary-school-teachers-conceptions-common/docview/2244370710/se-2>.
- [49] Cragg, L., Richardson, S., Hubber, P. J., Keeble, S., & Gilmore, C. (2017). When is working memory important in arithmetic? The impact of strategy and age. *PLoS One*, 12(12), 1-8. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0188693.
- [50] Cruz, M. (2019). A proposed supplementary teaching materials in teaching grade 7 mathematics: its acceptability. *International Journal of Secondary Education*. 7. 6. 10.11648/j.ijsedu.20190701.12.
- [51] Cui, J., Xiao, R., Ma, M., Yuan, L., Kodash, R. C., & Zhou, X. (2020). Children skilled in mental abacus show enhanced non-symbolic number sense. *Current Psychology*, 1-14.
- [52] Daniel, L. M., Gonulates, F., Hodgson, T., & Brewer, M. (2020). The long-term impact of a coherence-based model for mathematics intervention. *School Science and Mathematics*, 120(4), 220-231. Doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/ssm.12399>.
- [53] Das, A. (2017). Structuring self-instructional material for LIS distance education: Role of instructional design theory. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 7(3), 170-176. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/structuring-self-instructional-material-lis/docview/1989248478/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [54] Department of Education (2015). Order no. 12. Guidelines on the early language, literacy, and numeracy program. Manila, Philippines.
- [55] Department of Education Memo No. 127, s.2014, "administration of school year (sy) 2014-2015 national achievement test (NAT) and numerical supplementary for primary grades (LAPG)".
- [56] Department of Education. (2020). New guidelines and validation tool in locally developed learning resources.
- [57] Diletti, J. S. (2017). *Teacher Concerns and the Enacted Curriculum of the Common Core State Standards in High School Mathematics* (<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/teacher-concerns-enacted-curriculum-common-core/docview/1979945783/se-2>).
- [58] Dolan, E. (2020). Growing a growth mindset: Characterizing how and why undergraduate students' attitudes change. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 1-19.
- [59] Donolato, E., Giofrè, D., & Mammarella, I. C. (2019). Working memory, negative affect, and personal assets: How do they relate to mathematics and reading literacy? *PLoS One*, 14(6) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0218921>.
- [60] Dwijayani, N. M. (2021). Mathematical concepts. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1918(4) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1918/4/042066>
- [61] Eleni, D., Kalliopi-Evangelia, S., & Andreas, L. (2020). Comparative evaluation of virtual and augmented reality for teaching mathematics in primary education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(1), 381-401. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-09973-5>.

- [62] Ellingsen, R., & Clinton, E. (2017). Using the Touch Math program to teach mathematical computation to at-risk students and students with disabilities. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 41(1), 15-40. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/using-touchmath-program-teach-mathematical/docview/1939743465/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [63] Emerson, P. & Gamboa, A. (2020). Affecting mathematics performance of junior high school students. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics*. Vol 15(1), 34-37.
- [64] Evans, Danielle; Field, Andy P. (2020): Supplementary material from "Math's attitudes, school affect and teacher characteristics as predictors of math's attainment trajectories in primary and secondary education." The Royal Society. Collection. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.5136154.v2>.
- [65] Fastame, M. C., Manca, C., Penna, M. P., Lucangeli, D., & Hitchcott, P. K. (2019). Numeracy skills and self-reported mental health in people aging well. *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 90(3), doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11126-019-09655-y>.
- [66] Fourie, J., Sedibe, M., & Muller, M. (2018). The experiences of foundation phase teachers regarding reading literacy interventions at an underperforming school in Gauteng province. *Interchange*, 49(1), 85-109. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10780-017-9311-4>.
- [67] Freeman, H. (2018). *Developmental predictors of early numeracy outcomes*. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/developmental-predictors-early-numeracy-outcomes/docview/2083996424/se-2>.
- [68] French, D. (2002). *Teaching and learning algebra*. (London: A&C Black)
- [69] Frongillo, E. A., Kulkarni, S., Basnet, S., & de Castro, F. (2017). Family care behaviors and early childhood development in low- and middle-income countries. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 26(11), 3036-3044. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10826-017-0816-3>.
- [70] Gafoor, A. (2015). Learner and teacher perception on difficulties in learning and teaching mathematics: some implications. *Online Submission*.
- [71] Ganor-Stern, D. (2017). Can dyscalculics estimate the results of arithmetic problems? *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 50(1), 23-33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0022219415587785>.
- [72] Geary, D. C. (2015). Development and Measurement of Preschoolers' Quantitative Knowledge. [doi: 10.1080/10986065.2015.1016823]. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 17(2-3), 237–243.
- [73] Geary, D. C., Hoard, M. K., Nugent, L., & Scofield, J. E. (2021). In-class attention, spatial ability, and mathematics anxiety predict across-grade gains in adolescents' mathematics achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 113(4), 754. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/edu0000487>.
- [74] Genç, M., & Çolakoğlu, Ö. M. (2021). Modeling the effects of instructional quality on mathematical literacy performance from the students' perspective: PISA 2012 turkey sample. *Egitim Ve Bilim*, 46(206) <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/modeling-effects-instructional-quality-on/docview/2529843046/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [75] Glenn, A. L. (2016). Design experiments: Theoretical and methodological challenges in creating complex interventions in classroom settings. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 2(2): 141-178. 232.
- [76] Gresko, R. A., & Vassiliki (Vicky) I Zygouris-Coe. (2020). Supporting disciplinary literacy and science learning in grades 3–5. *The Reading Teacher*, 73(4), 485-499. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/trtr.1860>.
- [77] Gunawan, I., Subandi, Yuberti, Satiyarti, R. B., Kamelia, M., & Nabila, L. (2019). The development of physics props made from se materials as a form of care for the environment. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1155(1) doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1155/1/012016>.
- [78] Gunduz, Erol Mehmet. (2017). Playing With Clay: Knowledge Making Across Physical and Digital Materials. <https://www.proquest.com/docview/1928948882/B6CEE7422A864E86PQ/1>.

- [79] Handayani, S., Adisendjaja, Y. H., & Kusnadi. (2021). Musi estuary ecosystem alternative teaching materials as supplementary books for biology learning in high schools. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1806(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1806/1/012155>.
- [80] Hatta, Miterianifa, & Octarya, Z. (2021). Promoting scientific literacy in chemistry learning on the subject colloid through instructional material development. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1842(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1842/1/012045>.
- [81] Hiniker, A., Rosenberg-lee, M., & Menon, V. (2016). Distinctive role of symbolic number sense in mediating the mathematical abilities of children with autism. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 46(4), 1268-1281. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10803-015-2666-4>.
- [82] Hojnoski, R. L., Caskie Grace, I. L., & Miller, Y. R. (2018). Early numeracy trajectories: Baseline performance levels and growth rates in young children by disability status. *Topics in Early Childhood Special Education*, 37(4), 206-218. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0271121417735901>.
- [83] Hoven, C. W., Amsel, L. V., & Tyano, S. (2019). An international perspective on disasters and children's mental health. *An International Perspective on Disasters and Children's Mental Health*, doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15872-9>.
- [84] Hua, H., Zhou, S., Ding, Z., & Pan, Y. (2018). The change mechanism of human-environment interactions from contextualization: A case study of the Hong Hani rice terraces as a world cultural heritage site. *Sustainability*, 10(7), 2230. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su10072230>.
- [85] Hugo, A. J., & Masalesa, M. J. (2021). Realizing that the out-of-school environment could influence the development of foundation phase learners' literacy skills. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 11(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v11i1.840>.
- [86] Hulse, T., Daigle, M., Manzo, D., Braith, L., Harrison, A., & Ottmar, E. (2019). From here to there! Elementary: a game-based approach to developing number sense and early algebraic understanding. *Educational Technology, Research, and Development*, 67(2), 423-441. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11423-019-09653-8>.
- [87] Hwang, S. (2020). Examining the effect of students' early numeracy activities at home on later mathematics achievement via early numeracy competencies and self-efficacy beliefs. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 13(1), 47-56. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26822/iejee.2020.172>.
- [88] Jacobs, J., Seago, N., & Koellner, K. (2017). Preparing facilitators to use and adapt mathematics professional development materials productively. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 4(1), 1-14. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40594-017-0089-9>.
- [89] Jara-Ettinger, J., Piantadosi, S., Spelke, E. S., Levy, R., & Gibson, E. (2017). Mastery of the logic of natural numbers is not the result of mastery of counting: evidence from late counters. *Developmental Science (Online)*, 20(6) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/desc.12459>.
- [90] Jatisunda, M. G., Hidayanti, M., Lita, Dede, S. N., Cahyaningsih, U., & Suciawati, V. (2021). Mathematical knowledge for early childhood teaching: A deep insight on how pre-service teachers prepare mathematical activities. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1778(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1778/1/012017>.
- [91] Jiang, P. (2021). Gender differences in mathematics academic performance of high school students in western China. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1978(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1978/1/012038>.
- [92] Jimenez, B. A., & Besaw, J. (2020). Building early numeracy through virtual manipulatives for students with intellectual disability and autism. *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 55(1), 28-44. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/building-early-numeracy-through-virtual/docview/2367743138/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [93] Jimenez, B. A., & Stanger, C. (2017). Math manipulatives for students with severe intellectual disability: A survey of special education teachers. *Physical Disabilities*, 36(1), 1-12. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14434/pders.v36i1.22172>.
- [94] Jin, Z., Jiang, X., Wang, X., Liu, Q., Wang, Y., Ren, X., & Qu, H. (2021). *NumGPT: improving numeracy ability of generative pre-trained models*. Cornell University Library, arXiv.org.

- [95] Johnsen, S. K. (2020). A formative evaluation of differentiation practices in elementary cluster classrooms. *Roeper Review*, 42(3), 206-218. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02783193.2020.1765921>.
- [96] Jonas, N. (2018). *Numeracy practices and numeracy skills among adults*. St. Louis: Federal Reserve Bank of St Louis. <https://www.proquest.com/working-papers/numeracy-practices-skills-among-adults/docview/2072928533/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [97] Jones, J. B. (2017). To the transfer: Critical race theory and a transfer receptive culture1. *Community College Review*, 49(3), 343-345.
- [98] Kamboj, P., & Singh, S. K. (2015). Effectiveness of selected teaching strategies about the learning styles of secondary school students in India. *Interchange*, 46(3), 289-312. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10780-015-9253-7>.
- [99] Kaminski, J. & Sloutsky, V. (2020). The use and effectiveness of colorful, contextualized, student-made material for elementary mathematics instruction. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 1-23.
- [100] Kang, C. Y., Duncan, G. J., Clements, D. H., Sarama, J., & Bailey, D. H. (2019). The roles of transfer of learning and forgetting in the persistence and fadeout of early childhood mathematics interventions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(5), 590. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/edu0000297>.
- [101] Kani and Shahrill (2015). Applying the Thinking Aloud Pair Problem Solving Strategy in Mathematics Lessons. *Asian journal of management science and education* Vol. 4(2).
- [102] Kannianen, L., Kiili, C., Tolvanen, A., Aro, M., & Leppänen, P.,H.T. (2019). Literacy skills and online research and comprehension: struggling readers face difficulties online. *Reading and Writing*, 32(9), 2201-2222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11145-019-09944-9>.
- [103] Karimah, R. K. N., Kusmayadi, T. A., & Pramudya, I. (2018). Analysis of difficulties in mathematics learning on students with guardian personality type in problem-solving HOTS geometry test. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1008(1) doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1008/1/012076>.
- [104] Kazhan, Y., Hamaniuk, V., Amelina, S., Tarasenko, R., & Tolmachev, S. (2020). The use of mobile applications and Web 2.0 interactive tools for students' German-language lexical competence improvement.
- [105] Khun-Inkeeree, H., Omar-Fauzee, M. S., & Othman, M. K. H (20216). The Mathematics Performance of Primary School Students' in Southern Thailand.
- [106] Kim, G. B. (2017). *The effect of e-based virtual manipulative on third-grade elementary students' algebraic thinking in math education*. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/effect-e-based-virtual-manipulative-on-third/docview/1896603130/se-2>.
- [107] Kleemans, T., Peeters, M., Segers, E., & Verhoeven, L. (2012). Child and home predictors of early numeracy skills in kindergarten. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 27, 471-477.
- [108] Kluczniok, (2017). Early family risk factors and home learning environment as predictors of children's early numeracy skills through preschool. *Journal sage public*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244017702197>.
- [109] Kristoffersen, I. (2017). The Metrics of Subjective Wellbeing Data: An Empirical Evaluation of the Ordinal and Cardinal Comparability of Life Satisfaction Scores. *Social Indicators Research*, 130(2), 845-865. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11205-015-1200-6>.
- [110] Kurmanaviciute, R., & Stadskeiv, K. (2017). Assessment of verbal comprehension and non-verbal reasoning when standard response mode is challenging: A comparison of different response modes and an exploration of their clinical usefulness. *Cogent Psychology*, 4(1).
- [111] Kurniasih, A. W., Hidayah, I., & Asikin, M. (2020). Developing mathematics learning materials of the fifth grade of elementary school integrating mathematics game, problem posing, and manipulative. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1567(2).

- [112] Kurniawati, H., & Triyanta. (2021). A simple solar energy heater was developed as a stem-based instructional material for high school students. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1918(2)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1918/2/022044>.
- [113] Lee, H. K., & Ahram, C. (2020). Enhancing early numeracy skills with a tablet-based math game intervention: A study in Tanzania. *Educational Technology, Research, and Development*, 68(6), 3567-3585. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09808-y>.
- [114] Lee, M. (2019). *An exploration of number sense, motivation, and mindset about math achievement for middle school students with learning disabilities*. (<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/exploration-number-sense-motivation-mindset/docview/2203505610/se-2>).
- [115] Lestari, N. D. S., Juniati, D., & Suwarsono, S. (2019). Integrating mathematical literacy toward mathematics teaching: A prospective math teacher's pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) in designing the learning task. *IOP Conference Series. Earth and Environmental Science*, 243(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/243/1/012131>.
- [116] Lidon, L. (2019). A reflective analysis of the selection and production of instructional material for curriculum delivery at the primary level in postcolonial Guyana. *Sage Open*, 9(2) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/2158244019858445>.
- [117] Limeri, L., Carter, N., Choe, J., Harper, H., Martin, H., Benton, A., & Dolan, E. (2020). Growing a growth mindset: Characterizing how and why undergraduate students' attitudes change. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 1-19.
- [118] Lindmeier, A., Seemann, S., Kuratli-Geeler, S., Wullschleger, A., Dunekacke, S., Leuchter, M., Vogt, F., Elisabeth, M. O., & Heinze, A. (2020). Modeling early childhood teachers' mathematics-specific professional competence and its differential growth through professional development – an aspect of structural validity. *British Society for Research into Learning Mathematics. Research in Mathematics Education*, 22(2), 168-187.
- [119] Love, M. L., & Ewoldt, K. B. (2021). Implementing asynchronous instructional materials for students with learning disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 57(2), 132-137. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/10534512211001847>.
- [120] Lu, Y., Wen-Juo Lo, & Lincoln, F. (2017). Effects of intervention on self-regulated learning for second language learners. *Chinese Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 40(3), 233-260.
- [121] Maloney, E. Ramirez, G., Gunderson, E., Levine, S., & Beilock, S. (2015). Intergenerational Effects of Parents' Math Anxiety on Children's Math Achievement and Anxiety. *Association for Psychological Science*.
- [122] Manches, A., & O'Malley, C. (2016). The effects of physical manipulatives on children's numerical strategies. *Cognition and Instruction*, 34(1), 27-50.
- [123] Manguilimotan, R. (2019). Attitudes, study habits, and academic performance of junior high school students in mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(3), 547-561.
- [124] Mardiana, D., & Cahyani, R. (2018). The development of basic natural science learning materials to improve students' competence. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1028(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1028/1/012206>.
- [125] Mashoedah, Hartmann, M., Herman, D. S., & Zamroni. (2020). Developing instructional media integrated with learning style instruments for industrial electronics study programs of vocational high schools. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1456(1) Doi: [HTTP://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1456/1/012044](http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1456/1/012044).
- [126] Mathematics anxiety reduces default mode network deactivation in response to numerical tasks mathematics learners. *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 6(2), 8-15.
- [127] Matthews, N. C. (2021). *Accessible instructional materials and disabled student success*. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/accessible-instructional-materials-disabled/docview/2579716358/se-2>.
- [128] Meiqian, W., & Xudong, Z. (2021). Using game-based learning to support learning science: A study with middle school students. *The Asia - Pacific Education Researcher*, 30(2), 167-176. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40299-020-00523-z>.

- [129] Meke, K. D. P., Jailani, J., Wutsqa, D. U., & Alfi, H. D. (2019). Problem-based learning using manipulative materials to improve student interest in mathematics learning. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1157(3)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1157/3/032099>.
- [130] Melhuish, E., Phan, M., Sylva, K., Sammons, P., Siraj-Blatchford, I., & Taggart, B. (2020). Effect of the home learning environment and preschool center experience upon literacy and numeracy development in early primary. *Journal of social issues*. <https://doi.org/10.1231/j.1540-4560.2008.00550.x>.
- [131] Melhuish, E., Phan, M., Sylva, K., Sammons, P., Siraj-Blatchford, I., & Taggart, B. Effect of the home learning environment and preschool center experience upon literacy and numeracy development in early primary. *Journal of social issues*. <https://doi.org/10.1231/j.1540-4560.2008.00550.x>
- [132] Merav, H., & Avidov-Ungar Orit. (2020). The integration of digital game-based learning into the instruction: Teachers' perceptions at different career stages. *TechTrends*, 64(6), 887-898. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11528-020-00503-6>.
- [133] Metikasari, S., Mardiyana, & Triyanto. (2019). Mathematics learning difficulties of slow learners on A circle. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1227(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1227/1/012022>.
- [134] Michael, I. (2015). *Factors leading to poor performance in mathematics subject in Kibaha Secondary Schools* (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).
- [135] Mick, B. (2020). The convergence of gaming and learning: Higher education should pivot to a game-based instruction model. *Planning for Higher Education*, 48(2), 20-24.<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/convergence-gaming-learning-higher-education/docview/2401308572/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [136] Miller, E., Severance, S., & Krajcik, J. (2021). Motivating teaching, sustaining change in practice: Design principles for teacher learning in project-based learning contexts. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 32(7), 757-779.
- [137] Miller, T. (2018). Developing numeracy skills using interactive technology in a play-based learning environment. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5(1), 1-11. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40594-018-0135-2>.
- [138] Missall, Hojniski, Caskie and Repasky, (2015). Home numeracy environment of pre-schoolers: examining relations among mathematical activities, parent mathematic beliefs, early mathematic skills. *Early education and development* Volume 26. Issue 3. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2015.96824.3>.
- [139] Montes, M., & Contreras, L. C. (2021). The pedagogical knowledge deployed by a primary mathematics teacher educator in teaching symmetry *Mathematics*, 9(11), 1241. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/math9111241>.
- [140] Moon, J., & Park, Y. (2021). A scoping review on open educational resources to support interactions of learners with disabilities. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 22(2), 314-341. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v22i1.5110>.
- [141] Moraová, H. (2017). Do authors of online electronic materials for teaching mathematics use their potential to use non-stereotypical cultural settings? *EJEL. Electronic Journal of E-Learning*, 15(3), 235-243.
- [142] Morgan, K., Bianca MCW, v. B., McCormack, T., & McGourty, J. (2018). The prevalence of specific learning disorders in mathematics and comorbidity with other developmental disorders in primary school-age children. *British Journal of Psychology*, 109(4), 917-940. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/bjop.12322>.
- [143] Moustafa, A. A., Porter, A., & Megreya, A. M. (2020). Mathematics anxiety and cognition: An integrated neural network model. *Reviews in the Neurosciences*, 31(3), 287-296. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/revneuro-2019-0068>.
- [144] Muhammad, J. A., Tariq, M. K., & Hussain, T. (2017). Validation of screening checklist for learning difficulties in mathematics. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 39(2) Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/validation-screening-checklist-learning/docview/1984751809/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [145] Mulligan, J., Oslington, G., & English, L. (2020). Supporting early mathematical development through a 'pattern and structured intervention program. *ZDM*, 52(4), 663-676.

- [146] Muneer, S. (2021). Women empowerment, and access to education in Pakistan: Barriers within the home. *Journal of the Research Society of Pakistan*, 58(2), 32. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/women-empowerment-access-education-pakistan/docview/2506205722/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [147] Mustam, A. A., & Adnan, M. (2019). Perception of primary mathematics teachers on STEM-oriented teaching and learning. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1227(1) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1227/1/012009>.
- [148] Namkung, J. M., & Nicole, B. (2021). The Effects of Algebraic Equation Solving Intervention for Students with Mathematics Learning Difficulties. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 54(2), 111-123. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0022219420930814>.
- [149] Nelson, G., & McMaster, K. L. (2019). The effects of early numeracy interventions for preschool and early elementary students: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(6), 1001. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/edu0000334>.
- [150] Nikolov, M., & Timpe-Laughlin, V. (2021). Assessing young learners' foreign language abilities. *Language Teaching*, 54(1), 1-37. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0261444820000294>.
- [151] Nirit, F., Hadad Bat-Sheva, & Orly, R. (2021). Non-symbolic-magnitude deficit in adults with developmental dyscalculia: evidence of impaired size discrimination but intact size constancy. *Psychological Science*, 32(8), 1271-1284. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0956797621995204>.
- [152] Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (2018). *Creating Effective Teaching and Learning Environments*. <https://www.oecd.org/education/school/43023606.pdf>
- [153] Özkubat, U., & Özmen, E. R. (2021). Investigation of Effects of Cognitive Strategies and Metacognitive Functions on Mathematical Problem-Solving Performance of Students with or Without Learning Disabilities *. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 13(4), 443-456. <http://dx.doi.org/10.26822/iejee.2021.203>.
- [154] Paghubasan, E. (2017). Developing students' problem-solving skills and attitudes in mathematics through game-based and activity-oriented assessment styles. *Research funded by Basic Education Research Fund (BERF), DepEd-Regional Office, Carpenter Hill, Koronadal City, Region XII, Philippines*.
- [155] Peng, P., Wang, T., Wang, C., & Lin, X. (2019). A meta-analysis on the relationship between fluid intelligence and reading/mathematics: Effects of tasks, age, and social-economic status. *Psychological Bulletin*, 145(2), 189.
- [156] Perbowo, K. S., Maarif, S., & Pratiwi, A. (2019). Perception of mathematics teachers in marginal regions toward using ICT and manipulative tools as learning media. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1315(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1315/1/012042>.
- [157] Pletzer, B., Kronbichler, M., Nuerk, H. C., & Kerschbaum, H. H. (2015). Performance in Biology in senior secondary schools in Osun State. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(9), 705-709
- [158] Prabowo, A., ASIH, & Jumardi. (2018). Lesson study on grader of elementary school to improve the student's numeracy skill. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 983(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/983/1/012077>.
- [159] Pradana, L. N., & Sholikhah, O. H. (2019). Mathematical literacy training (MLT) through virtual-based mathematics kits (VMK) for best mathematics performance. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1318(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1318/1/012017>.
- [160] Pradana, L. N., & Sholikhah, O. H. (2019). Mathematical literacy training (MLT) through virtual-based mathematics kits (VMK) for best mathematics performance. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1318(1) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1318/1/012017>.
- [161] Press, M., & Meiman, M. (2021). Comparing the impact of physical and digitized primary sources on student engagement. *Portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 21(1), 99-112. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/comparing-impact-physical-digitized-primary/docview/2484285142/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [162] Purpura, D. J., Schmitt, S. A., & Ganley, C. M. (2017). Foundations of mathematics and literacy: The role of executive functioning components. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 153, 15-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2016.08.010>.

- [163] Purpura, Logan, Das, and Napoli,. (2017). Why do early mathematics skills predict later reading? The role of mathematical language. *Developmental psychology*. Volume 53(9). 1633-1642.
- [164] Raghubar, K., and Barnes, M. (2016). Early numeracy skills in preschool-aged children: a review of neurocognitive findings and implications for assessment and intervention. *The clinical neuropsychologist* volume 31. Issue 2. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13854046.2016.1259387>.
- [165] Ren, X. (2019). The undefined figure: Instructional designers in the open educational resource (OER) movement in higher education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(6), 3483-3500. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-09940-0>.
- [166] Riccomini, P., Smith, G., Hughes, E., & Fries, K. (2015). The language of mathematics: The importance of teaching and mathematical learning vocabulary. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 31(3), 235-252.
- [167] Rice, M. F., & Ortiz, K. R. (2021). Evaluating digital instructional materials for K-12 online and blended learning. *TechTrends*, 65(6), 977-992. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11528-021-00671-z>.
- [168] Roberts, J., Phipps, S., Subeeksingh, D., Jaggernauth, S. J., Ramsawak-Jodha, N., & Dedovets, Z. (2020). Reflection on the effects of concrete mathematics manipulatives on student engagement and problem-solving in three secondary schools in Trinidad and Tobago. *Caribbean Curriculum*, 27 Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/reflection-on-effects-concrete-mathematics/docview/2564164692/se-2>.
- [169] Romano, R. (2019). *Comparing the effects of bea-selected and teacher-selected math interventions*. (<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/comparing-effects-bea-selected-teacher-math/docview/2240033850/se-2>).
- [170] Ruiz-Valenzuela, J. (2020). Job loss at home: Children's school performance during the great recession. *SERIEs*, 11(3), 243-286. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13209-020-00217-1>.
- [171] Rusdi, Fauzan, A., Arnawa, I. M., & Lufri. (2020). Designing mathematics learning models based on realistic mathematics education and literacy. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1471(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1471/1/012055>.
- [172] Rusmining, Purwanto, A., & Sumargiyani. (2019). Analysis of content components and context components of mathematics literacy on linear algebra. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1188(1)<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1188/1/012003>
- [173] Saar, V., Levänen, S., & Komulainen, E. (2018). Cognitive profiles of finnish preschool children with expressive and receptive language impairment. *Journal of Speech, Language and Hearing Research (Online)*, 61(2), 386-397.
- [174] Salihi, L., Aro, M., & Räsänen, P. (2018). Children with learning difficulties in mathematics: Relating mathematics skills and reading comprehension. *Issues in Educational Research*, 28(4), 1024-1038. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/children-with-learning-difficulties-mathematics/docview/2393077215/se-2>.
- [175] Samad, F., & Salasa, M., (2021). Improving numeracy skills through long kali leng traditional games teaching early math to young learners. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1832(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1832/1/012031>.
- [176] Sasanguie, D., De Smedt, B., & Reynvoet, B. (2017). Evidence for different magnitude systems for symbolic and non-symbolic numbers. *Psychological Research*, 81(1), 231-242. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00426-015-0734-1>.
- [177] Sasanguie, D., De Smedt, B., & Reynvoet, B. (2017). Evidence for different magnitude systems for symbolic and non-symbolic numbers. *Psychological Research*, 81(1), 231-242.
- [178] Schoen, R. C., Champagne, Z., Whitacre, I., & McCrackin, S. (2021). Comparing the frequency and variation of additive word problems in united states first-grade textbooks in the 1980s and the common core era. *School Science and Mathematics*, 121(2), 110-121.
- [179] Seel N. (2016). *Assimilation theory of learning*. In: Seel n.m. (eds) encyclopedia of the sciences of learning. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1428-6_3.

- [180] Segers, Kleemans and Verhoeven (2015). Role of parent literacy and numeracy expectations and activities in predicting early numeracy skills. *Mathematical thinking and learning* vol. 17. Issue 2-3.
- [181] Septianawati, T. and Puspita, E. (2017). Ethno mathematics study: uncovering units of length, area, and volume in Kampung Naga Society *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*8121012021.
- [182] Septianawati, T. and Puspita, E. (2017). Ethnomathematics study: uncovering units of length, area, and volume in Kampung Naga Society *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*8121012021.
- [183] Shaheen, R., Kanaya, Z., & Alshehada, K. (2020). The chromatic game number of generalized Petersen graphs and Jahangir graphs. *Journal of Applied Mathematics*, 2020 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2020/6475427>.
- [184] Sitompul, R. S. I., Budayasa, I. K., & Masriyah. (2018). Mathematics literacy of secondary students in solving simultaneous linear equations. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 947(1) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/947/1/012019>
- [185] Skwarchuk, S.-L., Sowinski, C., & LeFevre, J. (2014). Formal and informal home learning activities about children's early numeracy and literacy skills: A home numeracy model development. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 121, 63-84.
- [186] Smith, K & Shillam, P. (2015). An evaluation of food safety training using videotaped instruction. *Foodservice Research International*. 12, 41-50.
- [187] Sotos, J. (2021). Physical Fitness Fuels Greater Cognitive Power. *United States Naval Institute Proceedings*, 147(1). <https://www.proquest.com/trade-journals/physical-fitness-fuels-greater-cognitive-power/docview/2486550012/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [188] Sowell. (2021). Effect of manipulative materials in mathematics instruction. *National council teachers of mathematics*. Vol. 20 Issue 5, pages 498-505.
- [189] Spear, K. (2021). *Open Educational Resources in Missouri Public Schools: A Phenomenological Study of the Adoption Process* (Order No. 28540144). Available from Publicly Available Content Database. (2533172127). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/open-educational-resources-missouri-public/docview/2533172127/se-2>
- [190] Sugilar, Rajati, T., & Achmad. (2021). A hierarchical component model of students' difficulties learning mathematics in distance higher education. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1918(4) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1918/4/042053>.
- [191] Suparman, Juandi, D., & Tamur, M. (2021). Review of problem-based learning trends in 2010-2020: A meta-analysis study of the effect of problem-based learning on Indonesian students' mathematical problem-solving skills. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1722(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1722/1/012103>.
- [192] Tekir, Serpil; Akar, Hanife. (2019). The current state of instructional materials education: aligning policy, standards, and teacher education curriculum. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Egitim Bilimleri*; Vol. 19, Iss. 1, (Feb 2019): 22-40. DOI:10.12738/estp.2019.1.043.
- [193] Ten Braak, D., Lenes, R., Purpura, D. J., Schmitt, S. A., & Størksen, I. (2022). The cognitive processing potential of infants: Exploring the impact of an early childhood development program. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 7(1).
- [194] The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (2020). Access to equity in Mathematics Education. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 60.
- [195] Throndsen, Jennifer E., (2018). *Relationships among preschool attendance, type, and quality and early mathematical literacy*. <https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/etd/7043>.
- [196] Throndsen, Jennifer E., (2018). "Relationships Among Preschool Attendance, Type, and Quality and Early Mathematical Literacy" develop students' scientific attitude and natural science performance. *Eurasia Journal Of Mathematics, Science, And Technology Education*, 14(1), 61-76. 7043. <https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/etd/7043>.

- [197] Tikhomirova, T., Kuzmina, Y., & Malykh, S. (2018). *Does symbolic and non-symbolic estimation ability predict mathematical achievement across primary school years* towards the development of students' scientific attitude and natural science performance. *Eurasia Journal of mathematics, science and technology education*, 14(1), 61-76. <http://dx.doi.org/10.151/itmconf/20181804006>.
- [198] Trusz, S. (2018). Four mediation models of teacher expectancy effect students' mathematics and literacy outcomes. *Social Psychology of Education: An International Journal*, 21(2), 257-287. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11218-017-9418-6>.
- [199] Tsang, J. M., Blair, K. P., Bofferding, L., & Schwartz, D. L. (2015). Learning to "see" less than nothing: putting perceptual skills to work for learning numerical structure. *Cognition and Instruction*, 33(2), 154-197.
- [200] Tunstall and Ferkany (2017). The role of mathematics education in promoting flourishing. For the learning of mathematics vol.37 no. 1 pp. 25-28. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44382742?seq=1>.
- [201] Ubah, I. J. A., & Bansilal, S. (2018). Pre-service primary mathematics teachers' understanding of fractions: An action-process-object-schema perspective. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 8(2)<http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v8i2.539>.
- [202] Ubah, I. J. A., & Bansilal, S. (2018). Pre-service primary mathematics teachers' understanding of fractions: An action-process-object-schema perspective. *South African Journal of Childhood Education (SAJCE)*, 8(2) <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v8i2.539>.
- [203] Ulandari, L., Amry, Z., & Saragih, S. (2019). Development of Learning Materials updating students' mathematics school students with learning difficulties. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, 12, 154.
- [204] Van't Noordende, J., Volman, M., Leseman, P., Moeller, K., Dackermann, T., & Kroesbergen, E. (2018). The use of local and global ordering strategies in number line estimation in early childhood. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1562.
- [205] Vankúš, P. (2021). A systematic review, the influence of game-based learning in mathematics education on students' affective domain. *Mathematics*, 9(9), 986. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/math9090986>.
- [206] Verbos, J. (2018). *Non-symbolic Exact Quantity Representation in a Language-Impaired* <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/non-symbolic-exact-quantity-representation/docview/2169923284/se-2>.
- [207] Waymouth, H. (2018). Transforming teaching and learning: A review of 0RW1S34RfeSDcfkexd09rT2no more telling as teaching: Less lecture, more engaged learning. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 62(3), 352-354. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/jaal.896>.
- [208] Westera, W. (2019). Why and how serious games can become far more Why do early mathematics skills predict later mathematics and reading achievement? The role of executive function. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 214, 105306.
- [209] Wilkey, E. D., Pollack, C., & Price, G. R. (2020). Dyscalculia and typical math achievement are associated with individual differences in number-specific executivefunction. *Child Development*, 91(2), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13194>.
- [210] Williams, C. (2018). Learning to Write with Interactive Writing Instruction. *The Reading Teacher*, 71(5), 523-532. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/trtr.1643>.
- [211] Williamson, C. (2018). Engaging students in the learning process: The learning journal. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 27(2), 183-199.
- [212] Windschitl, M., Thompson, J., & Braaten, M. (2020). *Ambitious science teaching*. Harvard Education Press.
- [213] Wu, M. (2018). Educational Game Design as Gateway for Operationalizing Computational Thinking Skills among Middle School Students. *International Education Studies*, 11(4), 15-28.
- [214] Wulandari, N. P., Safitri, A. S., Novitasari, D., Salsabila, N. H., & Suliani, M. (2021). The effect of using worksheets on students' number sense ability. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1776(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/17426596/1776/1/012023>.

- [215] Yazlık, D. Ö., & Çetin, İ. (2020). Examining the Relationship between Mathematics Anxiety and Mathematics Teaching Anxiety of Prospective Mathematics Teachers. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 11(3), 646-667. <http://dx.doi.org/10.16949/turkbilmate.605951>.
- [216] Yilmaz, Z. (2017). Young Children's Number Sense Development: Age-Related Complexity across Cases of Three Children. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 9(4), 891-902.
- [217] YodaIK. (2017). The Development of Cooperative Learning Model Based on Local Wisdom of Bali for Physical Education Sport and Health Subject in Junior High School IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering1801012166.
- [218] Yolcu, A. (2021). Turkey's Problem-Solving Child: A Historical Analysis of the Cultural Spaces of Mathematics Education. *Egitim Ve Bilim*, 46(206) <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/turkey-s-problem-solving-child-historical/docview/2529848429/se-2?accountid=37719>.
- [219] Yuen Sze, M. T., Joshua, J. A., & Yaro, K. (2019). Developing theoretical coherence in teaching and learning: Case of neuroscience-framed learning study. *International Journal for Lesson and Learning Studies*, 8(3), 229-243. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/IJLLS-10-2018-0072>.
- [220] Zhang, D., Chan, W., & Yang, Y. (2021). The association between cognitive activation and mathematics achievement: A multiple mediation model. *Educational Psychology*, 41(6), 695-711. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2021.1917520>.
- [221] Zhang, H., Chang, L., Chen, X., Ma, L., & Zhou, R. (2018). Working memory updating training improves mathematics performance in middle school students with learning difficulties—frontiers in human neuroscience, 12, 154.
- [222] Zhao, Z. (2019). *Data-driven storytelling for casual users* (Order No. 13887051). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/data-driven-storytelling-casual-users/docview/2305846123/se-2>.